

EFFECTS OF STRESS ON THE HUMAN BODY

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Abstract: The thesis discusses the concept and types of stress, its impact on the human body.

Key words: stress, hypertension, occupational deformation, post-stress injury, leukocytes, mental disorders, oncological diseases, stressor

In the world, the processes of globalization, the acceleration of scientific and technical progress, and the increase in environmental problems pose a serious threat to the issue of human health. The reason for this is the development of the manufacturing industry, the reduction of manual labor, and the reduction of activities that make up a healthy lifestyle. The concept of stress has been assessed by the World Health Organization as a "disease of the 21st century", because stress occurs in any person, and the world's professions have already assessed this concept as a "global epidemic". [2] Stress symptoms are more common in people who interact with people. Professional deformation occurs as a result of emotional, personal exhaustion under the influence of many external and internal factors in the conditions of strong professional communication.

Stress is a state of extreme excitement and nervousness that occurs as a result of strong influences in humans and animals. Stress is a process characterized by a non-specific reaction of the body and stereotypic changes in the activity of the nervous and endocrine systems, caused by various extreme factors that threaten to disrupt homeostasis. The term "stress" was defined by the Canadian physiologist G. Selye and introduced into medicine (1936). In a person, stress of the same intensity can be both dangerous and positive. The initial state of the organism is of great importance in the emergence of diseases under the influence of stress.

When stress is limited to unpleasant sensations (muscle tension, sweating, shortness of breath, and anxiety), it can have a negative effect on a person. Unfortunately, chronic stress leads to the development of serious diseases. Diseases of the cardiovascular system are also among them. As mentioned above, stress causes high blood pressure. It is clear that stress has a bad effect on the cardiovascular system. Many scientists have analyzed the influence and role of emotional stress in the manifestation of blood pressure.

Stress directly affects the heart. Due to the effects of the sympathetic division of the autonomic nervous system and the above-mentioned hormones, its contraction and the number of heart attacks increase. With stress in the body, cholesterol and other fatty acids are shown. Cholesterol in the blood accumulates on the walls of blood vessels and disrupts blood flow in various parts of the body. If blood flow to the heart is impaired, the risk of death from heart disease or myocardial infarction is high, which leads to a lack of oxygen to the heart. Leukocytes are the most important component of the immune system. Leukocytes are divided into 3 groups: phagocytes and two types of lymphocytes (T-cells and B-cells). These groups of cells have one job: they detect and destroy foreign substances in the body. Any factor that reduces the number of leukocytes poses a threat to human health. Stress refers to such factors. People with severe losses have reduced immune system function. Women who survive divorce have 40% lower levels of killer cells than normal (cells that fight viruses and tumors). [1]

The state of stress occurs in different diseases in its own way. Especially in oncological diseases, the state of stress manifests itself in its own way. In this regard, the work of O.A. Vorona on the topic "Psychological consequences of stress in patients with breast cancer" (2005) confirms our opinion. In the theoretical part of the research: stress and oncological diseases, the role of psychological factors in the course and etiology of oncological diseases, psychological reactions and mental disorders arising as a result of the diagnosis and treatment of oncological diseases, post-traumatic stress disorders in oncological patients were studied. So, O.A. According to Vorona's research, the number of post-stress injuries and the individual's use of coping strategies to get out of them are directly related to the tendency to develop or recover from the disease. [3] Using visualization skills and other techniques, if the number of lymphocytes decreases under stress, their number increases during treatment. As a result, the immune system can control cancer cells to some extent. However, this method of cancer treatment is not widely recognized and is used only experimentally. As a result of stress in the digestive system, the secretion of saliva in the mouth decreases. That's why when we're worried, everything in our mouth feels dry.

Due to stress, the muscles of the esophagus may start to contract uncontrollably, and there may be difficulties in swallowing. During chronic stress, the secretion of noadrenaline causes spasm of gastric capillaries, which prevents mucus secretion and destroys the protective mucous barrier in the

stomach walls. This unimpeded hydrochloric acid (which increases during stress) damages tissue and can reach blood vessels, causing bleeding ulcers. Modern medicine admits that all disorders in the field of bile and pancreas, pancreatitis, any problems related to the stomach are related to stress. In the area of muscles, the muscles become weak under the influence of stress. Most of us don't understand muscle tension. Stress also affects smooth muscle function. Thus, a migraine headache is the result of the contraction and dilation of the carotid arteries 110 on one side of the head. The reduction phase is often accompanied by sensitivity to light and noise, irritability, flushing, or pale skin. When the arteries dilate, certain chemicals irritate the adjacent nerve endings and cause pain.

Stress-induced muscle tension headaches can affect the forehead, jaw, and even the neck. Chronic stress can cause muscle spasms and back pain, just like a headache that causes muscle tension. In a stressful situation, a person sweats more and the surface temperature of the skin drops. Because norepinephrine causes the walls of blood vessels on the surface of the skin of the hands and feet to contract, fingers and toes freeze more than usual during times of stress. In addition, narrowing of blood vessels is observed. Thus, when nervous, anxious people are often under stress, their skin is cold, slightly moist and dull. Long-term release of glucocorticoids leads to a significant decrease in testosterone production. This reduces sexual desire and leads to impotence. Stress is one of the causes of menstrual disorders in women, which leads to reproductive dysfunction.

In conclusion, it can be said that there are positive and negative aspects of stress. The main beneficial feature of stress is, of course, a natural function of a person's adaptation to new conditions. In addition, the "beneficial" consequences of stress include an increase in stress tolerance, the development of personal qualities and personal growth, and the realization of the need for strength. Stress is harmful when it is too intense or lasts too long. Among the negative consequences of stress, there are many mental reactions such as deterioration of performance of specified tasks, impairment of mental tasks, fatigue, post-traumatic stress disorder, mental illnesses and psychological problems. In addition, stress is the main reason for the development of psychosomatic diseases.

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